

Exploiting digital twins and metaverse technologies for the digital transformation of City transportation

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Abstract. Digital Twins (DT) of future cities/regions provide an accurate and reliable reference as they seamlessly integrate the physical, digital and human worlds and allow stakeholders to assess the impact of planned interventions before investments and implementations are made. METACITIES is an Excellence Hub that spans a large geographical area, that of Southeastern Europe, represented by three innovation ecosystems in Cyprus, Greece, and Bulgaria. Each ecosystem is Quadruple Helix Model-based and involves partners representing scientific, industrial, civic, and public sectors. They aim to collaboratively define and implement common digital Research and Innovation strategies, policies, and joint projects-pilots, orchestrated towards the benefit of the citizens, the stakeholders of the regional innovation ecosystems and the growth of the whole south-east European region.

A key expected outcome of METACITIES is the development and adoption of an Open Digital Twin framework (ODTF) that facilitates the collaborative development of Digital Twins of complementary future city domains, focusing on use cases with high social impact such as Smart Mobility, Energy Efficient Buildings and Urban Planning, while conducting a socio-techno-economic requirements analysis.

In this paper, the strategic objectives, methodology, the quadruple helix model of collaboration of the Excellence Hub and the way these are applied to the digital transformation of the City's mobility sector are presented. Aspects to be addressed include monitoring of traffic volume, identification and tracking of emergency incidents, real-time information and notifications on parking availability, etc.

Keywords: Digital Twins, Metaverse, Smart Mobility.

1 Introduction

1.1 Current State of DTs and Metaverse in Southeast Europe

The technological landscape of digital twins [1], [2] and metaverse [3] in Southeast Europe is diverse and rapidly evolving [4]. While there are notable advancements and early adopters in the region, more work is needed to ensure that all countries can benefit from the potential of these technologies. Addressing infrastructure and technological readiness together with relevant policy, capacity-building, and funding challenges is crucial to unlocking the full potential of digital twins and metaverse technologies in the area. The implementation of Digital Twins (DTs) plays a transformative role and Smart mobility is an area where digital twins are gaining traction. They are being employed to optimize public transportation networks, predict traffic patterns, and manage fleets of autonomous vehicles. Some countries in the Southeast Europe region have started implementing digital twins to support their smart mobility initiatives, while others are still exploring the potential benefits.

The metaverse viewed as a collective virtual shared space that merges the physical and digital worlds while heavily relying on Mixed Reality (MR) technologies, on the other hand, is an emerging concept globally [5], [6]. Though still in its infancy in the region of SEE, a few pioneering initiatives [7] led by innovative start-ups, research institutions, and technology companies exploring the metaverse's possibilities in various sectors, such as gaming, education, and cultural heritage, indicate a growing momentum towards developing and adopting the metaverse.

Despite the growing interest in digital twins and metaverse, there are several challenges that the region must overcome to embrace this emerging technology fully. These challenges include, among others, limited access to high-speed internet, the need for significant investments in digital infrastructure, and the development of local talent and skills in VR and AR/XR technologies. However, these challenges also present opportunities for regional cooperation, knowledge exchange, and joint investments. And this is where the METACITIES Excellence Hub finds its *raison d'être*.

1.2 Goals of the Excellence Hub

METACITIES is a project funded by the European Union, WIDERA Call. The project's strategic vision is to exploit advanced and emerging digital technologies to empower all stakeholder types of the Quadruple Helix (QH) model, namely, interconnected companies, research and academic institutions, governmental bodies, and societal actors, to mutually reinforce each other and synergistically raise the level of smart

city/region innovation. To that effect METACITIES establishes an Excellence Hub that spans a large geographical area, that of Southeast Europe (SEE), represented by three location-based innovation ecosystems in Cyprus, Greece, and Bulgaria. Each regional innovation ecosystem consists of partners representing all stakeholder types of the QH, strong within their territorial context, with a proven track record and expertise in the technologies under consideration and long experience in using them. By mobilizing the forces of these three ecosystems, the Excellence Hub works towards the collaborative design and implementation of common digital R&I strategies, policies, and joint pilots orchestrated towards the benefit of the citizens, the stakeholders, the local ecosystems and the growth of the whole SEE region at large. Innovation excellence is strengthened in the involved place-based ecosystems through cross-border collaboration in the selected domain of cutting-edge science and innovation. The collaboration is founded upon an elaborate joint R&I strategy, a nexus of collaborative links across sectors including research, innovation, and outreach activities as well as business and sustainability plans.

To that respect METACITIES' purpose is to provide support to cities, regions, and infrastructure providers regarding the implementation of DTs and metaverse as means for evaluating and measuring the impact of specific policies and decisions in the various aspects of the city. DTs and metaverse technologies will enable policymakers to manage the introduction of various ICT systems and optimize technology utilization to achieve societal objectives and maximize benefits [8],[9].

Digital Twins and Metaverse Technologies for Smart Mobility are addressed by both the Greek and the Cypriot innovation ecosystems and within the context of the project and the Excellence Hub, the two ecosystems develop joint R&I Strategies and Implementation Plans towards a collaborative, mutually beneficial approach, while aligning and fusing local, regional and national strategic plans for digital transformation.

1.3 Joint R&I Strategic Plans for Smart Mobility

Formulating the “unified” METACITIES Joint R&I strategy for adoption of digital twins and metaverse technologies for smart cities and smart regions aims to define a framework to join the efforts of the involved ecosystems for speeding up the process of smart city development, addressing the challenges, seizing the cross-border collaboration opportunities, and ultimately contributing to the vision for the development of more sustainable, efficient, and resilient urban systems in the region.

The ecosystems worked towards the definition of common objectives and priorities of their local R&I Strategies for smart cities and regions. Identified commonalities center around the following issues:

- Digital Transformation and Innovation
- Connectivity and Infrastructure Development for Digital Transformation
- Sustainable Economic Growth and Social Inclusion
- Environmental Sustainability, Low-Carbon Economy and Green Transition
- Transport and Digital Connectivity
- Enhancing Education, Digital Skills and Human Resources
- Research, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship.

Specifically for the Smart Mobility area the involved ecosystems have framed the scope of their related activities by specializing their objectives in the targeted sector, as shown in the following table.

	Strategic Goal	Smart and Safe Mobility Objectives
1	Digital Transformation and Innovation	Create user-friendly and interoperable digital platforms for access to real-time traffic, parking availability, and incident information for citizens.
2	Connectivity and Infrastructure Development for Digital Transformation	Implement a digital infrastructure and network system, based on open data and technologies, to monitor traffic flow and parking occupancy, and manage incidents.
3	Sustainable Economic Growth and Social Inclusion	Promote smart mobility initiatives to enhance social inclusion for socially sensitive groups (e.g. smart parking) and foster sustainable economic growth.
4	Environmental Sustainability, Low-Carbon Economy and Green Transition	Encourage the adoption of eco-friendly transportation options and promote the use of public transit systems for all.
5	Transport and Digital Connectivity	Enhance and advocate for digital connectivity to provide real-time mobility information and data.
6	Enhancing Education, and Digital Skills and Human Resources	Strengthen education and digital skills development initiatives to build a skilled human resource base supporting smart mobility solutions.
7	Research, Innovation and Entrepreneurship	Foster entrepreneurship in research and innovation to drive advancements in smart mobility solutions.

2 Quadruple Helix Collaboration Model for Smart Mobility

Today's smart city movement is a bottom-up approach through which the perspectives of various stakeholders are considered in arriving at a consensus, in contrast to a public-led top-down method that dictates a particular vision of the city to all people involved [8]. Stakeholders are defined as agents that are interested, affected or that have power to influence the development of Smart Sustainable Cities [9]. Application of the QH requires the establishment of a horizontal cooperative system among all stakeholders in each smart city intervention. The types of possible involvement of stakeholders are quite diverse ranging from deriving service demand to service supply and operation management. Identifying the unspoken needs and respecting the aspiring expectations of diverse stakeholders are important priorities of policymakers and strategic planners.

In a QH-based Smart City Reference Collaboration Model, a smart city is envisaged as a collaborative ecosystem allowing for the co-creation of sustainable, future proof innovations that improve life in the city and boost the economy, in which technology plays an enabling role. These collaborative ecosystems promise to contribute to the

facilitation of knowledge exchange among the ecosystem actors. Smart cities serve as an innovation broker, connecting different stakeholders, allowing for real-life ideation, co-creation and validation.

In the smart city as a collaborative ecosystem conceptual model, values are offered and gained between the stakeholders. Values are distinguished into Social (e.g., safer streets) and Economic (e.g., generation of revenue). The concept of Social Value refers to for example, reducing traffic jams, reducing pollution, reducing the time to find a convenient parking spot, increasing neighborhood cohesion, etc. Economic Value on the other hand covers economic metrics such as the annual economic growth of cities and companies within the city, a decrease in unemployment, new businesses (start-ups) and increased sustainability, etc.

In the Quadruple Helix (QH) model adopted by the METACITIES project [10], the interconnections and value flows among the four stakeholder groups—Public Sector, Business, Academia, and Citizens—are integral to the success of smart mobility initiatives. The Public Sector acts as orchestrators, setting policies and regulations that guide the development of urban mobility solutions. Business partners, encompassing technology providers and urban service developers, leverage these regulations to innovate and implement cutting-edge solutions. Academia plays a vital role by contributing research, knowledge, and expertise, helping to bridge the gap between theoretical advancements and practical implementation. Citizens, as active participants, offer real-world insights and feedback, influencing decision-making and ensuring that the solutions align with community needs. This interconnected ecosystem creates a dynamic flow of value—information, expertise, and resources—enabling a collaborative and holistic approach to smart mobility. The symbiotic relationships among these stakeholders not only facilitate the co-creation of innovative solutions but also ensure that the resulting smart mobility initiatives are adaptive, sustainable, and responsive to the evolving needs of the community.

2.1 QH-based Value Flow Analysis for Smart Mobility

Analysis of values gained and offered by each stakeholder type of the QH model in a smart mobility context is presented below.

Public Sector - Governmental Entities:

- Values Offered: The public sector brings forth a spectrum of values crucial to smart mobility initiatives. As the primary driver of urban policies and infrastructure development, the public sector contributes funding programs, regulatory frameworks, and strategic planning. Furthermore, its engagement in demographic considerations ensures that smart mobility solutions are inclusive, meeting the diverse needs of the local populace. Through technological integration and the implementation of healthcare advancements, the public sector introduces innovative solutions for medical transportation, emergency response systems, and telemedicine, thus generating social value. In economic terms, the public sector provides a stable and supportive environment, attracting businesses and fostering innovation through collaborations in the smart mobility sector.

- **Values Gained:** Conversely, the public sector reaps substantial benefits from the collaborative engagement within the Quadruple Helix. Through partnerships with academia, industry, and civil society, the public sector gains access to cutting-edge technologies, research insights, and innovative solutions. Collaboration with the academic sphere brings forth research findings and knowledge that inform evidence-based policymaking. Engaging with industry provides the public sector with economic insights, business innovation, and job creation opportunities. This reciprocal relationship results in a dynamic exchange of expertise, resources, and innovations, positioning the public sector as a key beneficiary in the collaborative ecosystem of the Quadruple Helix.

Businesses:

- **Values Offered:** Companies in the technology sector offer their technological expertise, resources, and innovative technologies in smart mobility projects. This might involve the design and implementation of sensor-based IoT networks, or the creation of user-friendly mobile applications. Additionally, businesses can also provide services related to the installation, maintenance, and troubleshooting of the deployed smart mobility technology.
- **Values Gained:** Businesses stand to gain significantly from their involvement in smart mobility projects. Not only do they get access to new business opportunities and markets, but they can also utilize the data generated through the smart mobility systems for improving their products and services. Furthermore, their active involvement in public service initiatives allows them to have access to new data and customer bases, and benefit from enhancing their corporate image showcasing them as leaders in smart city solutions.

Academia:

- **Values Offered:** Academic institutions can leverage their research capabilities, scientific expertise and innovation potential to offer new ideas and theoretical models for smart mobility. They can also contribute state of the art relative infrastructures (sensors, actuators, backed platforms, car/driver simulators) to yield novel technologies, techniques, algorithms and end-to-end services for smart mobility. They can contribute with research on urban mobility, statistical analysis of parking demand, handling congestion in real time, drivers' behavioral analysis, traffic optimization, pedestrian and cyclists' flows, or even research on the social and environmental impacts of smart mobility.
- **Values Gained:** For academia, participation in smart mobility R&I activities offers an opportunity to apply their research knowledge, expertise and developments in practical, real-world scenarios, thereby enhancing the relevance and applicability of their research. This strengthens significantly their position in the respective ecosystems and enable them to pursue more actively additional collaboration, funding as well as dissemination to prestigious scientific forums and publications. Collaborations with public and business entities can also pave the way for more research funding and partnership opportunities. They also gain access to a wealth of new data, both from the public sector and from the

implemented smart mobility systems, that can be utilized for further research particularly related to AI based techniques and algorithms development in relation to traffic management, increased traffic safety and others.

Citizens:

- Values Offered: The value offered by citizens that are involved in the city issues and are participating in the evolution of their city environment is very valuable to the smart mobility solution design and implementation. Citizens can offer their real-life experiences, insights, valuable feedback and local knowledge on the city's mobility situation and issues. They can participate in surveys and focus groups and can also be involved in the development and testing phases of new smart mobility interventions, offering for example their feedback on the user interface and functionality of smart mobility apps, and their overall experience with new systems. Engaged citizens can be involved in the co-design of specific pilots, in the specification of requirements and the initial proof of concept trials.
- Values Gained: In return, citizens benefit from improved mobility services and an inclusive, transparent mobility framework that has been co-designed by citizens. They can enjoy a more seamless and stress-free driving and parking experience, which can also reduce traffic congestion and contribute to a cleaner urban environment. Enabling citizens to influence the shape of their urban living, leads to increased civic satisfaction, a sense of ownership, and stronger community bonds. The most significant value citizens gain is the direct improvement to their living environment and the enhancement of public services, which can lead to a higher quality of life.

3 Methodology and Implementation Plan

This section highlights the methodology and the implementation plan the METACITIES project's partners should follow to reach the objectives of their Joint Strategy with respect to the Smart and Safe Mobility priority area. It outlines the strategic approach and practical steps to be taken in order to achieve the Joint Strategy's objectives of the specific priority.

Main part of the overall methodology is the definition of Vision and Goals. The vision of the METACITIES Strategy has been defined as follows and it is aligned with broader economic and societal goals:

"to improve quality of life and experience of citizens, enhance urban efficiency and create a more connected, responsive, inclusive and environmentally conscious urban environment, through integration of innovative Smart city technologies, digital connectivity, data-driven solutions and sustainable practices, optimizing the use of resources and services that foster economic growth."

Following a common agreement on the vision of this integrated Strategy, the METACITIES partners proceeded in further outlining specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound goals to guide the strategy's implementation. These goals have been derived from the analysis made on each ecosystem's local characteristics and

priorities in the sector of Digital Twins and Metaverse Development in South-east Europe and the merging of their common elements. Usually an R&I strategy encompasses various priority areas and sectors to foster economic development, competitiveness, and sustainability within a specific geographic region. The specific priorities may vary, based on the region's strengths, challenges, and developmental goals. In the present document we focus on the Priority Area of Smart and Safe Mobility.

3.1 Smart and Safe Mobility Action plan

Planning is necessary to map out what you need to do in order to achieve the goals. When referring to a Strategy's Implementation Plan, we mean the process used to ensure a strategic plan is executed. It involves translating the high-level goals and objectives outlined in the strategic document into specific actions and initiatives that can be carried out by the relevant stakeholders. Once a strategic plan is prepared, an implementation plan is necessary to map out how to bring the strategic plan to life. The implementation plan then breaks down tasks into identifiable actions, assigns tasks and responsibilities to the people involved, and creates a timeline.

Similarly, in the case of the METACITIES' Joint Strategy, the Implementation Plan aims at defining and specifying actions as a means to reach the objectives set out above. The exact implementation plan for each of the objectives and goals is out of the scope of the paper, however some indicative actions are enlisted here as they form part of the Action Plan and Use case description that will be discussed in the following section.

Proposed Actions for Objective 1 (see Table above):

- Develop a centralized mobile application providing real-time traffic updates, incident notifications, and alternative routes (possibly leverage upon visualization capabilities offered by Digital Twin and Metaverse technologies).
- Develop and support a common architecture and an open framework that can inter operate with all digital platforms and services. Establish open APIs for collaboration with third-party developers to enhance and expand digital platforms and Digital Twins.
- Conduct user experience studies to ensure the accessibility and user-friendliness of the digital platforms.

Proposed Actions for Objective 2 (see Table above):

- Invest in the deployment of smart sensors and IoT devices for real-time monitoring of traffic conditions (pilot and large scale).
- Develop a centralized command and control center to manage incidents efficiently using data analytics and AI. This should include Digital Twins for the city transport system that enables imposing application scenarios (pilot and large scale).
- Collaborate with private sector partners and academia to build and maintain a robust digital infrastructure.
- Support the common adaption of technical requirements for digital platform and data interoperability

3.2 Smart and Safe Mobility Use Cases in Patras

Smart mobility solutions play a pivotal role in addressing contemporary urban challenges, especially in densely populated areas like the Municipality of Patras. With the aim of leveraging technological innovations to foster sustainable urban development, the METACITIES project has emerged as a promising initiative. This section delves into the goals, existing infrastructure, and the role of Digital Twin technology in augmenting smart mobility within the Municipality of Patras.

Goals based on existing problems: The Municipality of Patras faces several mobility-related challenges that hinder the efficiency and sustainability of urban transportation systems. These include traffic congestion, illegal parking, inadequate public transportation information, limited electric vehicle infrastructure, and environmental concerns. To address these pressing issues, the METACITIES project outlines comprehensive goals:

1. **Traffic Management:** Alleviating traffic congestion and mitigating the adverse effects of illegal and double parking on urban mobility.
2. **Parking Management:** Enhancing the availability of parking spaces and providing real-time information to optimize parking utilization.
3. **Public Transportation Optimization:** Improving the accessibility and reliability of public transportation through accurate information on bus arrivals and real-time tracking.
4. **Electric Vehicle Infrastructure:** Facilitating the transition to sustainable transportation by expanding the infrastructure for recharging electric vehicles.
5. **Environmental Monitoring:** Monitoring and managing environmental conditions, particularly air quality, to ensure a healthier urban environment.

Digital Twin Technology Integration: Digital Twin technology serves as a cornerstone in the METACITIES project, offering a dynamic and holistic approach to urban mobility management. Through the integration of various data streams and advanced analytics, Digital Twins enable real-time visualization, simulation, and optimization of urban systems.

Integration into Smart Cities Framework: All of these initiatives are integral components of the broader smart cities' framework, which aims to leverage technology and data-driven solutions to improve urban efficiency, sustainability, and quality of life. By integrating existing infrastructure into smart mobility solutions, the Municipality of Patras seeks to create a seamless and interconnected urban environment where citizens have access to real-time information, efficient transportation options, and sustainable mobility alternatives. Through collaborative efforts and innovative approaches, Patras is positioning itself as a leader in smart city development, paving the way for a more

livable and resilient urban future. In conclusion, the METACITIES project presents a transformative opportunity for the Municipality of Patras to enhance smart mobility and foster sustainable urban development. By leveraging Digital Twin technology alongside existing infrastructure investments, Patras can address its mobility challenges comprehensively. Through proactive management of traffic, parking, public transportation, and environmental conditions, Patras can pave the way towards a more efficient, resilient, and livable city for its residents and visitors alike.

2.2.1 Use case 1: Smart mobility and Parking behavior analysis

One of the main problems in the City of Patras that affects the quality of life, safety and accessibility of various significant points of interest in the city center are the limited parking spaces and limited short term parking solutions, large number of people living in the outskirts of the city and bad parking behavior with respect to short term parking. In order to propose solutions and policies that will overcome the problem of the illegal parking induced congestions compromising the safety and the accessibility of cyclists, pedestrians and drivers that visit or work at the city center, one need to understand the problem. In order to provide efficient and sufficient solutions the first step is to monitor the traffic patterns and characteristics, various parking related incidents and drivers/pedestrian behavior, in order to investigate and built an intelligent transport management system that may predict the effects of such illegal parking behaviors on the overall traffic and congestion.

High Level Technical Approach: In METACITIES we will provide the design for the functional blocks and respective interfaces for a Digital Twin that will evaluate all the data mentioned in the previous section, combining traffic data, parking solutions and data, illegal parking behavior and the effect that these will have on the traffic in the city center (e.g., a specific street). All the functional requirements will be defined and described. The Digital twin will be at the core of the Intelligent Transport and Incident Management System which will in turn show in a visual way the traffic situation of specific roads. In METACITIES, the digital twin will be able to visually exhibit the traffic situation and congestion in real time. Furthermore, the proposed digital twin should be able in the future to interface functional models and algorithms that may be able to train the behavioral models so that it will also be able to run specific what if scenarios in order to develop proposals for solving transport problems like optimization of traffic flow, pedestrian and cyclists flows, public transport alternatives, traffic management, parking management etc. In METACITIES the exact data flow, standards and interfaces will be sought and defined.

2.1.2 Use Case 2: Environmental behavior analysis on traffic incidents

One of the main problems faced by the big cities that compromise the quality of life of its citizens relates to the Green dimension of the city life. Especially for the Smart Mobility priority, environmental impacts have been identified as a compromising factor that needs to be dealt with for specific stakeholders (cyclists, pedestrians) but for all the

citizens at large. Monitoring the environmental indexes is a very important factor when trying to apply policies and actions that will make a City greener, healthier, more sustainable and more attractive for its citizens and visitors. The impact of traffic incidents on environmental indexes needs to be thoroughly analyzed by correlating traffic conditions with environmental (air quality, noise, smoke, etc.) measurements.

High Level Technical Approach : In METACITIES we will design the main functional blocks that will comprise a Digital Twin that will evaluate all the environmental (air quality, noise, smoke, etc) data, and traffic data in order to investigate the correlation that they have and the effect that traffic and /or incidents may have on the environment in the city center (e.g. a specific street).

2.1.3 Use Case 3: Emergency Management

One main problem in large cities that affects the quality of life and the safety of the citizens relates to the road deaths and injuries that through UN General Assembly Resolution 74/299 — a Second Decade of Action for Road Safety 2021–2030 are set to be reduced by at least 50%. It has become evident that for injuries, in case of road accidents, shorter response times can significantly reduce people’s permanent disability and death rates. To that respect an Intelligent Transport and Incident Management System of a smart City, according to the METACITIES R&I strategies and goals for Smart Transport priorities should alleviate the issues of traffic congestion for emergency services.

High Level Technical Approach: Based on real time collected data and analysis, we will design the building blocks, interoperability center and interfaces that are required to be built for the Digital Twin that will comprise an operating center for emergency services through which authorities can sync up their actions after a traffic incident. These actions include vehicle’s rerouting while facilitating emergency vehicles to access the incident when needed. At a later stage, this operating center will become an advanced notification system for drivers, cyclists, pedestrians and public vehicles.

3.3 Smart Mobility Requirements

Carrying out a comprehensive requirements’ analysis for the presented use cases on smart mobility, we conclude with a set of functional (Table 4) and non-functional requirements [16]. Functional and non-functional requirements are two types of specifications that define what an application should do and how well it should perform. Functional requirements describe the actions and interactions that users can perform with the app, while nonfunctional requirements describe the quality attributes and features of the app. Smart mobility digital twins are designed to help people move around the city with ease and convenience, using innovative technologies and solutions. They provide real-time information on the best routes, schedules, and prices for different mobility options, such as buses, trains, cars, bikes, etc. But smart mobility applications are

not only about convenience. They are also about quality and sustainability. They ensure that the mobility options they offer are user-friendly, reliable, secure, and scalable.

4 METACITIES Architecture for Smart Mobility.

The generic Digital Twin overall architecture is presented in [13]. A typical high level Digital Twin architecture for Smart Mobility is shown in the next diagram [13]-[16], and consists of three planes: the lower plane (in blue) stands for the physical world where humans, vehicles, and traffic infrastructures reside; the upper plane (in yellow) represents the digital space where the digital replicas of those physical entities are found; and the space between the physical and the logical planes, the communication plane plays a crucial role in this framework to allow real-time and non-real-time data streaming, both upstream and downstream.

The architecture described here is in line with [16]. Data are collected from a number of things in a transport environment, like IoT sensors and cameras, vehicles, as well as humans via mobile devices and applications or other mobility related devices. Additionally, data can be retrieved from simulators and field-use applications. The Edge Computing layer effectively handles actuation towards devices, allowing decisions made at the Logical space -Digital Twin layer to reliably reach the devices. Data from any sources are then fed into distributed real-time processing service buses that can perform filtering, routing, shaping, and processing. Furthermore, the Digital Twin layer is a series of microservices, closely (via IPC) or loosely (via Cloud APIs) interconnected between them. Those services carry the overall system intelligence, digital twin infrastructure, and AI/ML, and they rule execution subsystems and implement the decision-making outcome by issuing API requests towards the Edge Computing layers' advertised API endpoints. This layer allows the system to use data processing and analytics services in order to derive insights and patterns from the data ingested previously via the acquisition layers. These services can include various algorithms, machine learning models, statistical analysis, and other data processing techniques to extract valuable information. Additionally, the architecture incorporates models and simulations that replicate the behavior of the physical and logical objects of the "real world". These models allow the digital twin to predict future states, analyze what-if scenarios, provide recommendations, make decisions, actuate directly towards devices and third-party services, and create alerts.

The Network architecture of the communication plane suitable for METACITIES comprises the heart of the digital infrastructure as a necessary interconnection element for the data to be scouted, collected, processed and analyzed. The network will also allow actuation of specific interconnected elements and all user interaction with the digital infrastructure along with visualization of data. As it was described, Use Cases and applications that may be deployed in METACITIES, may require access to the data received from various mobile devices. Evidently, all the above sensing and IoT technologies will be interconnected to the edge and cloud with various network technologies and protocols. The list may contain other technologies as well, together with a list of corresponding gateways.

Fig. 1. Digital Twin architecture for Smart Mobility: the lower plane (in blue) stands for the physical world; the upper plane (in yellow) represents the digital space where the digital replicas of those physical entities are found; and the space between the physical and the logical planes, the communication plane.

Conclusions

We presented the METACITIES vision for future cities/regions DTs to provide an accurate and reliable reference as they seamlessly integrate the physical, digital and human worlds and allow stakeholders to assess the impact of planned interventions before investments and implementations are made. Especially regarding the Smart Mobility, we presented the QH-based collaboration model and an analysis of values exchanged among stakeholders, the methodology and implementation plan that meets all citizens' requirements for real-time information and notifications on parking availability, ability to pay using different payment methods, automatically identify valid people with disabilities, identify and track emergency incidents, monitor traffic volume, etc.

Based on the above we presented the METACITIES proposal for the first version of the generic Digital Twin architecture that depicts the initial blocks and requirements for the METACITIES digital architecture that can support the specific DTs and Metaverses that can lie at the core of the R&I Strategies.

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